

A factorial comparison of excess mortality models for Germany

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Abstract

Reliable estimates of excess mortality (EM) are essential for actuarial applications and for informing public debate and policy. During the COVID-19 pandemic, however, published EM estimates for Germany differed by tens of thousands of deaths, raising concerns about their methodological robustness.

We therefore construct a comprehensive factorial framework for estimating expected mortality, systematically varying six components: sex treatment, demographic data set, age cohort resolution, temporal resolution, forerun length, and mortality model form. In total, 1152 candidate models are fitted to German mortality data from 2000–2019 and extrapolated to 2020–2024; unstable combinations are excluded. Model performance is assessed using post-hoc residuals, the fraction of variance unexplained (FVU), and the resulting EM estimates. Our results show that EM estimates are largely insensitive to sex stratification and temporal aggregation, but highly sensitive to age cohort resolution, forerun length, and model form. In particular, models without age stratification yield implausibly high EM due to aggregation effects consistent with Simpson’s paradox, while constant and quadratic models produce unstable extrapolations. By contrast, actuarial models with moderate forerun lengths provide robust and interpretable results.

We therefore recommend excluding constant and quadratic baselines, avoiding unstratified models, and using updated demographic data when estimating excess mortality.

Keywords: excess mortality, mortality modeling, life tables, demographic data, age cohort resolution, temporal resolution, model sensitivity analysis, COVID-19 pandemic, Germany

1 Introduction

Mortality models are more than technical constructs: they are the silent backbone of life insurance mathematics, public health evaluation, and – in times of crisis – political decision making. A few thousand estimated deaths more or less can tilt public perception, steer pandemic policies, or shape the debate on vaccination and lockdown measures. The COVID-19 years (2020–2024) have shown vividly how estimates of *excess mortality* (EM), i.e. the difference between observed and expected deaths, are not mere academic exercises but contested numbers with real-world implications.

At the heart of mortality modeling lies the actuarial toolkit. A classical starting point is the *binomial model*, in which the number of deaths in a given population is treated as a binomially distributed random variable. When populations are large and death probabilities small, the *Poisson approximation* is typically used. Key ingredients are, on the one hand, *population series*, giving the number of living x -year-old males¹ and y -year-old females at 1 January of year t ($L_{x,t}$ and $L_{y,t}$, respectively), and, on the other hand, *life tables*, specifying age- and sex-specific mortality probabilities $q_{x,t}$ and $q_{y,t}$ for year t . While population size can be read from census data and official statistics, life tables must be fitted to observed mortality experience. This requires to know the population’s base year estimates and their long-term mortality trends of death rates.

During the COVID-19 years, the need to quantify EM brought these actuarial questions into the public spotlight. Estimates for Germany and elsewhere varied dramatically depending on modeling assumptions [2, 4, 5, 6, 7, 16, 17, 22, 24, 29]. For example, institutional estimates by Destatis [25] and the WHO [19] for 2020 differed by tens of thousands of deaths [23, fig. 4, app. C] from many academic models [17, 23], shaping headlines and public debates [27]. This raises a pressing scientific question: *How much of this discrepancy is driven by the choice of model structure rather than by genuine demographic uncertainty?*

While individual modeling choices have been discussed, such as whether to pool sexes or how to smooth short-term mortality fluctuations, there has been little systematic investigation into their *combined* effect. In particular, the second-order sensitivity of EM estimates, i.e. how one model component interacts with another (for example, age cohort resolution interacting with the choice of mortality model), remains underexplored. This lack of clarity is problematic: Without knowing which components matter most, and which may be safely simplified, EM estimates risk being inconsistent, irreproducible, or even misleading.

To address this gap, we construct a *factorial grid* of models for Germany, spanning the pre-COVID-19 years 2000–2019 and on through 2024. Six key components are varied:

1. **Sex treatment:** pooled vs. separate male/female mortality.
2. **Demographic dataset:** official *population tables* vs. *population pyramid*.
3. **Age cohort resolution:** all ages combined, 10-year, 5-year, or single-years cohorts.
4. **Temporal resolution:** yearly, monthly, weekly, or weekly with a moving-average filter.
5. **Forerun length:** 5, 10, or 20 years of historical data used for fitting, as a forerun to extrapolation.
6. **Mortality model form:** six alternatives, ranging from ‘constant’ baselines, over ‘linear’ and ‘quadratic’ descriptions, to actuarial trend models, which include standard and refined exponential formulations.

The full factorial design yields over a thousand candidate models, of which many are discarded due to instability or implausibility, leaving a large ensemble for systematic comparison. By confronting all of these models with the same German mortality data, we are able to map out not only the variability of EM estimates, but also their sensitivity to modeling assumptions, both individually and in interaction.

¹We follow the actuarial convention that x denotes male age and y denotes female age.

In doing so, this study contributes at two levels: First, for actuaries, it clarifies which model choices (e.g. forerun length, mortality model form) critically affect EM estimates, and which (e.g. sex pooling, short-term resolution) can be chosen more flexibly. Second, for public health and policy, it highlights the stakes: Poorly chosen models can exaggerate or even invert EM signals, whereas careful design yields robust and thus reliably interpretable results.

Our analysis demonstrates that there is no single “correct” model of excess mortality, but that some models are vastly more reliable than others. By making this explicit, we aim to strengthen the interpretability of mortality statistics, and to avoid misleading conclusions.

2 Data and methods

We briefly introduce the variables used to perform all calculations. Let $L_{x,t}$ and $L_{y,t}$ denote the absolute number of living x year old males (or y year old females, respectively) at the beginning of year t . Let further $M_{x,t}$ and $M_{y,t}$ denote the absolute (observed) number of deaths – or *mortality* – of x year old males (or y year old females, respectively) during year t . The number of living people $L_{\cdot,t}$ was taken from two alternative sources [8, 9], which will be elaborated in the next section. The mortality data $M_{\cdot,t}$ were exclusively taken from the “special analysis” (“Sonderauswertung”) of the German Federal Statistical Office (Destatis), who publish data regarding the years 2021-2025 separately [11] from the years 2000-2020 [10]. These data are collected regionally, and published by Destatis repeatedly and provisionally during a year. In addition, the data include the state in which the person died. After a plausibility check, reliably converged death data are made available in the fall of the following year. The converged numbers partly differ considerably from the preliminary ones: the plausibility check results in a correction of several 10,000 deaths, see the discussion in [18]. As the provisional data are no longer made available by Destatis, the tables containing all deaths counts before and after the plausibility check can be found in the Supplementary Material. Fig. 1 shows the difference between the provisional numbers and the finally converged version after the plausibility check for the exemplary year 2019. The data show a substantial correction of approximately 33% for the age cohort 0-30 years, while changes in the other age cohorts appear at as low as 2-3%. Additionally, these corrections are non-homogeneously distributed among German states, as shown alongside – with Bremen showing a massive post-hoc reduction in deaths by about 18%, while Brandenburg offered deaths counts increased by up to 16%. The difference between these two data sets should be considered as data uncertainty.

In order to perform model fitting and extrapolation, let then $q_{x,t}$ and $q_{y,t}$ denote the (model-) *estimates* for the observed mortality probabilities,

$$q_{x,t} \approx \frac{M_{x,t}}{L_{x,t}}, \quad q_{y,t} \approx \frac{M_{y,t}}{L_{y,t}} \quad (1)$$

of an x year old male (or y year old female, respectively) in year t . Given the estimated mortality probabilities for people of a certain age, the *expected* number of deaths D_t of the whole population in year t – to be compared to the observed mortality M_t of that population in that year – can now be calculated as follows. We start by equating the yearly sequence of expected numbers of deaths for males and females of a certain age with the yearly sequence of the observed numbers:

$$D_{x,t} = L_{x,t} \cdot q_{x,t}, \quad D_{y,t} = L_{y,t} \cdot q_{y,t}. \quad (2)$$

Here we ignore the ‘birthday problem’ that someone of age x at the beginning of the year only dies at age x if the time of death is before his birthday. To overcome this problem in most cases Far’s formula is used. For simplicity we just use Eqns. (1) and (2). Next, given a partition \mathcal{A} of ages into cohorts, e.g. 1-year, 5-year, 10-year, or all ages combined. We calculate the number of deaths in a year t in each age cohort $a \in \mathcal{A}$ by

$$D_{a,t} = \sum_{x \in a} D_{x,t} + \sum_{y \in a} D_{y,t}, \quad (3)$$

Figure 1: Deviation in deaths counts among age cohorts and German states. For age cohorts of 5 years (left) and states (right), the color codes indicate the percentage deviation between ‘initial’ and ‘converged’ death counts, calculated as $(M_{converged} - M_{initial})/M_{initial} \cdot 100$.

and the total number of expected deaths of the whole population in that year by

$$D_t = \sum_{a \in \mathcal{A}} D_{a,t} . \quad (4)$$

Next, a fit is performed for each model configuration over the yearly sequence $D_{a,t}$ (Eqn. (3)) of observed deaths across a predefined *forerun* period \mathcal{T} , i.e. an arbitrary but fixed set of years preceding the first year of intended extrapolation. Formally, the fitting minimizes the sum of squared residuals between the function $q_{a,t}$ of expectation and the observed $M_{a,t}/L_{a,t}$ values on a time-, sex-, and age-resolved grid (see Section 3). The fitting is carried out as an optimization using the *Trust-Region Reflective* algorithm as implemented in MATLAB (Mathworks, v. R2025a). This procedure not only calibrates the mortality model parameters (i.e. of the expected $q_{a,t}$ functions explicitly formulated in Section 3.6) but also implicitly smoothes (filters) high-frequency fluctuations in the raw (observed) mortality rates $M_{a,t}/L_{a,t}$, since all models (Section 3.6) enforce structural constraints on expected $q_{a,t}$ functions across ages and time. By applying meaningful model ideas, this procedure further allows an extrapolation (forecast) on years following \mathcal{T} .

After having calculated a model-based expectation D_t from the estimated mortality-rate functions – via Eqns. (1)–(4) and subsequent fitting – we evaluate two post-hoc performance measures in Section 4. First, the adjusted yearly fitting residual $R_{\mathcal{T},p}$ is defined as

$$R_{\mathcal{T},p} = \left(\frac{1}{|\mathcal{T}| - p} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (M_t - D_t)^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} , \quad (5)$$

where M_t denotes the observed total number of deaths in year t , and \mathcal{T} is the set of forerun years used for calibration. This residual measure accounts for the model’s ability to approximate given data. Crucially, the residual is evaluated exclusively at the level of yearly aggregated death counts. Consequently, both the number of observations $|\mathcal{T}|$ and the parameter count p entering the normalization refer only to the *yearly model fit*, and not to the full resolution of the mortality model itself. In particular, even if a model estimates age-, sex-, or time-resolved mortality rates

(e.g. weekly rates by single-years age cohorts), these numerous subdivisions do not increase $|\mathcal{T}|$ nor p in Eq. (5), as the model ultimately produces a single yearly expectation D_t per calendar year. The parameter count p therefore corresponds solely to the number of free parameters governing the temporal extrapolation of yearly mortality and is independent of demographic or temporal stratification. For example, a constant model fitted over a five-years forerun yields $|\mathcal{T}| = 5$ and $p = 1$, whereas a quadratic extrapolation over a 20-years forerun results in $|\mathcal{T}| = 20$ and $p = 3$. Further details on the parameterization of the individual model classes are provided in Section 3.

As a second reasonable requirement for a model is to reduce variance, we introduce as a second measure the fraction of variance unexplained (FVU, symbol $\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{T}}$) given by

$$\mathcal{V}_{\mathcal{T}} = \frac{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (M_t - D_t)^2}{\sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} (M_t - \bar{M}_t)^2} \quad , \quad (6)$$

which tells us whether our model is a better prediction than just taking the mean value as the expectation for the whole forerun period \mathcal{T} . Note that in a linear regression model this is exactly the unexplained variance.

In the second part of this paper (Section 5), we investigate the extrapolation of the models for the pandemic years 2020–2024. There, the EM $M_t - D_t$ for each year, and the mean EM (symbol \mathcal{E}) within the extrapolation period \mathcal{T}_{extrap} is of interest and measured by

$$\mathcal{E} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{T}_{extrap}|} \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}_{extrap}} (M_t - D_t) \quad , \quad (7)$$

which assesses the amount of people that are estimated to have died in excess of, or less than, the expected outcome. In the latter case, EM is negative thus indicating under-mortality.

3 Model framework for estimating expected mortality probabilities

In this section, we describe the modeling framework used to estimate expected mortality probabilities. These probabilities are derived from observed death counts and demographic exposure data by applying a structured set of methodological choices concerning how the data are stratified, aggregated, and extrapolated over time.

Each modeling choice constitutes an independent model component, and the Cartesian product of all admissible components defines the full factorial model space. Examples include whether mortality is modeled separately by sex or pooled, which demographic dataset is used, how finely ages are grouped, at which temporal resolution mortality is estimated, how long a historical period is used to calibrate trends, and which functional form is assumed for the mortality trend itself. Each component admits a finite set of alternative specifications.

Formally, each specification corresponds to a particular segmentation or aggregation of the underlying data, or to a particular functional assumption imposed during model fitting. Selecting one specification for each component uniquely defines a complete mortality model. The collection of all admissible specifications across all components therefore induces a full factorial grid of model variants. All model variants are treated on equal footing and are evaluated quantitatively using the same goodness-of-fit and excess-mortality criteria defined in Eqs. (5)–(7).

The overarching objective of the modeling process is thus not to identify a single “best” model *a priori*, but rather to construct, from observed demographic and mortality data, a comprehensive ensemble of expected mortality probabilities $q_{x,t}$ and $q_{y,t}$, covering all ages and calendar years, based on alternative but internally consistent modeling assumptions. These probabilities are obtained by smoothing historical mortality observation over time and, where required, extrapolating it into the pandemic period.

By organizing the analysis in this factorial manner, we are able to systematically assess how sensitive both the fitted baseline mortality and the resulting EM estimates are to individual modeling decisions as well as to their interactions. Accordingly, the following subsections describe

each model component separately, specifying the admissible alternatives and their mathematical implementation.

3.1 Demography data

Two official demographic datasets – as per description both based on the 2022 German census data – are provided by Destatis:

- *DPP*: the **d**ynamic **p**opulation **p**yramid as basis for demographic forecasts [8].
- *YPT*: **y**early **p**opulation **t**ables with recent methodological revisions and census corrections [9].

Both contain $L_{x,t}$ (males) and $L_{y,t}$ (females), i.e. the number of persons of a given age living on January 1 of year t . The percentage amount of deviation between DPP and YPT data series, normalized to YPT, is shown in Fig. 2. Particularly astounding is a deviation of up to 87% in the 91-95 year cohort in 2010, i.e. the population pyramid data contain 87% more people in this cohort than reported in the Genesis database (632,000 versus 337,200). On the other side, DPP contains only about 48% less of the 90-94 year olds in 2011 compared to the YPT (98,000 versus 191,100). The 1-years cohort resolution reveals that these differences are mainly to attribute to age cohorts during or after the two World Wars, e.g. age 82-87 in 2000 correspond year of birth 1913-1918 and age 55-60 in 2000 correspond to year of birth 1940-1945.

Figure 2: Deviation between demography data sets. For age cohorts of 5 years (left) and 1 year (right), the color codes indicate the percentage deviation between the DPP and the YPT demographic data set (calculated as $(L_{DPP} - L_{YPT})/L_{YPT} \cdot 100$).

3.2 Sexes

In a *separate-sex* model, we consider $q_{x,t}$ and $q_{y,t}$ separately, allowing for different base mortality levels and different time trends in male and female mortality. This reflects observed differences in mortality patterns between the sexes.

In a *uni-sex* (or *pooled*) model, we assume $q_{x,t} = q_{y,t}$ for $x = y$ and for all t , effectively pooling the mortality and demography data across sexes. This may be useful for reducing statistical variability in small samples or when sex-specific modeling is not required.

3.3 Age cohort resolution

Mortality probabilities may be estimated at different levels of age resolution:

- *All ages combined* (further referred to as ‘all-ages’): a single $q_{x,t} = q_t$ for the (entire, or male and female, respectively) population, regardless of demographic composition. This approach ignores age heterogeneity entirely and is therefore highly prone to aggregation bias.
- *10-years age groups*: $q_{x,t} = q_{a,t}$ constant for $x \in a$, where $a \subset \mathbb{N}$ spans 10 years. In the data sources used here, the youngest cohort contains all 0–29 year olds, while the oldest cohort includes everyone aged 90+ years. The remaining cohorts are defined as 30–39, 40–49, \dots , 80–89.
- *5-years age groups*: analogous definition for 5-years spans, i.e. 0–29, 30–34, 35–39, \dots , 90–94, 95+.
- *1-years age groups*: full resolution $q_{x,t}$ by single-years ages, i.e. $< 1, 1, 2, 3, \dots, 95, 95+$. This fine age cohort resolution is only available in yearly temporal resolution (see Section 3.4).

In general, finer resolution better reflects age-specific mortality variation, but requires a critical minimum of data in any cohort. This is particularly relevant at very young ages: the mortality of infants (< 1 year) is substantially higher than that of other individuals under 30, approaching levels otherwise only observed in middle adulthood. When broader cohorts (e.g. 0–29 years) are used, this effect is averaged out, potentially masking important age-specific mortality dynamics. At the same time, because the absolute number of infants is small relative to the total population, the numerical impact of this effect on overall EM is limited.

3.4 temporal resolution

The temporal resolution, at which death counts are aggregated, determines the smoothness and responsiveness of the model:

- *Yearly*: one mortality probability $q_{a,t}$ per calendar year.
- *Monthly*: twelve distinct mortality rates $q_{a,t_{m01}}, \dots, q_{a,t_{m12}}$ are calculated to capture seasonal effects while reducing short-term noise. All of these monthly mortality rates are multiplied with the population at the beginning of the year $L_{a,t}$ and summed up according to Eqns. (2)–(4) to yield the yearly number of deaths.
- *Weekly*: 52 distinct mortality rates $q_{a,t_{w01}}, \dots, q_{a,t_{w52}}$ are calculated – and likewise summed – to achieve the highest temporal resolution available in official statistics.
- *Weekly + moving-average filter*: similar to the weekly data, but smoothed by a moving average filter of 5-week width to reduce stochastic variation and account for varying delay in reporting of deaths.

A technical remark is in order: When aggregating monthly or weekly mortality rates to the yearly scale, we approximate exposures by the initial population $L_{a,t}$. Let $p_{x,t} = 1 - q_{x,t}$, exemplarily, be the survival rate of an x -years old male in year t . We can then estimate the error introduced by neglecting the decline of $L_{a,t}$ over the course of the year, by

$$q_{x,t} = 1 - p_{x,t} = 1 - \prod_m p_{x,t_m} = 1 - \prod_m (1 - q_{x,t_m}) = \sum_m q_{x,t_m} + \mathcal{O}(q_{x,t_m}^2),$$

where the last equality is a direct consequence of the inclusion-exclusion principle. Note that also q_{x,t_m} is estimated using the initial population at the beginning of the year. It follows that the yearly mortality rate is, to leading order, the sum of the monthly (or weekly) mortality rates, while higher-order terms are negligible for realistic probabilities $q_{x,t_m} \ll 1$.

3.5 Forerun of included data

The baseline mortality trend is fitted using a fixed historical window, forerun \mathcal{T} :

- *5 years*: prioritizes recency, sensitive to short-term trends, only few data points for numerical approximation.
- *10 years*: balance between trend stability and recency.
- *20 years*: long-term trend estimation, less sensitive to recent fluctuations.

3.6 Mortality models

We consider four distinct model families for the functions $q_{x,t}$ and $q_{y,t}$ of expected mortality.

- The *Generalized Exponential Mortality Model* (GEMM) with three independent fitting parameters $q_{x/y,t_0}$, $\beta_{x/y}$ and $\lambda_{x/y}$:

$$q_{x,t} = q_{x,t_0} \left(\beta_x + (1 - \beta_x) e^{-(t-t_0)\lambda_x} \right), \quad q_{y,t} = q_{y,t_0} \left(\beta_y + (1 - \beta_y) e^{-(t-t_0)\lambda_y} \right). \quad (8)$$

- The *Purely Exponential Mortality Model* (PEMM) of the German Actuarial Association (DAV, “Deutsche Aktuarvereinigung”) with two independent fitting parameters $q_{x/y,t_0}$ and $\lambda_{x/y}$, i.e. setting $\beta_{x/y} = 0$:

$$q_{x,t} = q_{x,t_0} e^{-(t-t_0)\lambda_x}, \quad q_{y,t} = q_{y,t_0} e^{-(t-t_0)\lambda_y}. \quad (9)$$

- The *Finite-limit Exponential Mortality Model* (FLEMM) with two independent fitting parameters $\beta_{x/y}$ and $\lambda_{x/y}$, i.e. setting $q_{x,t}(t_0) = \hat{q}_{x,t_0}$:

$$q_{x,t} = \hat{q}_{x,t_0} \left(\beta_x + (1 - \beta_x) e^{-(t-t_0)\lambda_x} \right), \quad q_{y,t} = \hat{q}_{y,t_0} \left(\beta_y + (1 - \beta_y) e^{-(t-t_0)\lambda_y} \right), \quad (10)$$

where

$$\hat{q}_{x,t_0} = \frac{M_{x,t_0}}{L_{x,t_0}}, \quad \text{and} \quad \hat{q}_{y,t_0} = \frac{M_{y,t_0}}{L_{y,t_0}} \quad (11)$$

denote the empirical mortality rates at $t = t_0$.

- The *Quadratic Mortality Model* (‘quadratic’) was based on the Taylor expansion of the PEMM at $t = t_0$ with an additional scaling parameter $\zeta_{x/y}$. Thus, three independent fitting parameters $q_{x/y,t_0}$, $\lambda_{x/y}$, and $\zeta_{x/y}$ determine the model as follows

$$q_{x,t} = q_{x,t_0} \left(1 - (t - t_0)\lambda_x + \frac{1}{2}\zeta_x(t - t_0)^2\lambda_x^2 \right), \quad q_{y,t} = q_{y,t_0} \left(1 - (t - t_0)\lambda_y + \frac{1}{2}\zeta_y(t - t_0)^2\lambda_y^2 \right). \quad (12)$$

- The *Linear Mortality Model* (‘linear’) with two independent fitting parameters $q_{x/y,t_0}$ and $\lambda_{x/y}$, using the Taylor expansion of the PEMM (and setting $\beta_{x/y} = 0$):

$$q_{x,t} = q_{x,t_0}(1 - (t - t_0)\lambda_x), \quad q_{y,t} = q_{y,t_0}(1 - (t - t_0)\lambda_y). \quad (13)$$

- The time-independent *Constant Mortality Model* (‘constant’) with one fitting parameter $q_{x,t}(t_0)$, setting $\beta_{x/y} = 1$:

$$q_{x,t} = q_{x,t_0} = q_x, \quad q_{y,t} = q_{y,t_0} = q_y. \quad (14)$$

The GEMM is the most natural and theoretically most plausible one, starting from a mortality level at time t_0 with decreasing mortality until it reaches the theoretical mortality level $q_{x,t_0}\beta_x$ or $q_{y,t_0}\beta_y$, respectively, at infinity.

Because this theoretical mortality level is, formally, a ‘bet on the future’, the DAV, as most actuarial associations, fixes $\beta_{x/y} = 0$ in a PEMM, while taking the parameters $\lambda_{x/y} \geq 0$ into account, terming them *longevity factors*, since exponential decreases have been observed in most Western countries in the last approximately 50 years, cf. [1, 3, 13, 17, 28]. In this study, we determine the base year t_0 by $t_0 = \min\{t \in \mathcal{T}\}$, although one may equivalently use $\max\{t \in \mathcal{T}\}$, as the DAV does, see DAV 2004R [13]. The actuarial model has the serious disadvantage that $q_{x,t}, q_{y,t} \rightarrow 0$ as $t \rightarrow \infty$ in Eqn. (9).

To avoid this unrealistic property $q_{x,t}, q_{y,t} \rightarrow 0$ of the PEMM, a non-zero limit was introduced in [22] yielding FLEMM. Similar to the PEMM, one would expect $\lambda_x, \lambda_y \geq 0$. FLEMM does not treat the base year mortality rate as a free parameter, but uses the observed initial value (i.e. $q_{x/y,t}$ at $t = t_0$) as a fixed point, while still being sensitive to the base mortality few years after t_0 .

The ‘linear’ and ‘quadratic’ mortality models are easier to implement [2, 15]; however, they have the disadvantage that mortality probabilities become negative (or > 1 if $\lambda_{x/y} < 0$) after a finite time horizon. Hence these models only make sense in the short term, while at least taking mortality trends into account.

In the most simple, ‘constant’ model, the mortality probabilities are constant over time, with $q_x, q_y \in [0, 1]$ estimated from data within the chosen historical forerun \mathcal{T} . It is well known that this is an unrealistic assumption in most Western countries, although sometimes it is claimed for older age cohorts [21, 26] that mortality is already close to a stable equilibrium with constant mortality probabilities. In the context of EM estimation in Germany, the ‘constant’ model was introduced in 2021 by Destatis [25] on a whole-population level, replacing the hitherto customary PEMM.

In common actuarial models, period life tables contain the base mortality probabilities for a given year and thus coincide with the ‘constant’ model. A generation life table contains also the longevity factors, which are estimated using historical data and smoothing algorithms. In Germany, for example the method of Whittaker-Henderson is applied, which consists of a logarithmic regression in time t and a spline interpolation for smoothing the results between different ages x, y . For more details on the method how to construct longevity trends in actuarial science, we refer to detailed explanations provided in [13].

In this study, mortality probabilities and longevity factors are merely considered as parameters free to be determined in least-squares fitting procedures. Hence, natural assumptions on the parameters like $q_{x/y,t} \in (0, 1)$, $\lambda_{x/y} \geq 0$, and $\beta_{x/y} \in [0, 1]$ are not necessarily satisfied. Therefore, the values of β_x, β_y , representing the proportion of mortality that remains asymptotically, may take values larger than 1, resulting in an increasing mortality rate over time, and $\lambda_{x/y}$ may become negative, yielding a diverging mortality (i.e. $q_{x/y,t} \rightarrow \infty$ if $\beta_{x/y} > 0$ or $q_{x/y,t} \rightarrow -\infty$ if $\beta_{x/y} < 0$).

Nevertheless, we want to point out that sometimes the observed mortality probabilities may in fact *increase* over certain time periods and if one aims at a model that reflects recent developments, then one should accept $\lambda_{x/y} < 0$ for short-term expectations, see the discussion in [20].

3.7 Summary of model grid

Combining all components would theoretically yield $2 \cdot 2 \cdot 4 \cdot 4 \cdot 3 \cdot 6 = 1152$ distinct models. However, the *one-year* age cohort resolution was only considered in combination with a *yearly* temporal resolution, as Destatis did only supply this coarser age for finer (monthly or weekly) temporal resolutions. After excluding these combinations, the number of models remaining for further analysis is given by

$$\left(1 - \frac{1}{4} \cdot \frac{3}{4}\right) \cdot 1152 = 936. \quad (15)$$

Each combination yields a specific model estimation of expected deaths expectation D_t , which is evaluated by its fitting residuals (Eqn. (5)), FVU (Eqn. (6)), and mean excess mortality (Eqn. (7)) in Germany between 2020 and 2024.

4 Evaluation of model fits

4.1 Elimination of unstable combinations from the grid

Before evaluating all initially feasible models, we performed a targeted audit (Fig. 3) to assess the model performances with respect to its sub-models. The top panel shows the death-time courses of all 936 feasible models. The six panels below stratify these trajectories by coloring according to one of the six model components:

1. *Sex treatment*: pooled vs. separate,
2. *Demography*: DPP vs. YPT series,
3. *Age cohort resolution*: all, 10-year, 5-year, 1-year,
4. *Temporal resolution*: yearly, monthly, weekly, weekly+filter,
5. *Forerun*: 5, 10, or 20 years,
6. *Mortality model form*: ‘constant’, ‘linear’, ‘quadratic’, PEMM, FLEMM, GEMM.

Figure 3: Expected death trajectories across model specifications. Top panel: overlay of all 936 feasible model trajectories of expected deaths D_t during 2000–2024 (gray lines); dots represent observed values. Lower six panels: the same trajectories, colored to distinguish the different choices within the six model components (sex treatment, demography, age cohorts, temporal resolution, forerun, mortality model form).

For some combinations of mortality model forms (point 6., see also Section 3.6) with specifications from one or more of the other five components (points 1.–5., see also Sections 3.1–3.5), we observed that the *expected* death counts D_t exhibited divergent or parameter-wise incohesive time courses: either an approximately exponential increase or decrease throughout 2020–2024 (highlighted in green or blue in Fig. 4), or distinctly gaping time courses (highlighted in red or blue in Fig. 4). The audit (Fig. 3) traced these pathologies primarily to four configurations:

- (i) the ‘constant’ model combined with a *10-* or *20-years forerun* (104 models),
- (ii) the GEMM combined with a *5-years forerun* (52 models),
- (iii) the GEMM with a *10-years forerun* under *weekly* temporal resolution (12 models), and
- (iv) the FLEMM with a *5-years forerun* under *weekly+filter* temporal resolution using *10-years age cohorts* (4 models).

The first three settings pair a highly flexible parametrization with either a very short forerun or a particularly fine temporal resolution. In practice, this fosters over-fitting of high-frequency deviations near the end of the forerun, which the Trust-Region Reflective optimizer translates into parameter combinations $(q_{t_0}, \beta, \lambda)$ (particularly with $\lambda < 0$) that imply unrealistically persistent, compounding increases in $q_{x,t}$ and $q_{y,t}$ across the extrapolation period. For some combinations of the GEMM and FLEMM model, expected mortality counts even diverged rapidly towards $\pm\infty$.

Consequently, as a first quality-control step, we excluded the above 172 configurations from all subsequent analyses, leaving 764 remaining models in the grid. This pruning prevents clearly non-plausible fits from distorting cross-model summaries while preserving the intended factorial exploration of defensible specifications.

Figure 4: Elimination of models. From all 936 model predictions (gray lines) those with particularly bad, unstable predictions were eliminated (colored lines). These include 104 combinations of the ‘constant’ model (red), 64 combinations of the GEMM (green), and 4 combinations of the FLEMM (blue). In consequence, 764 models were left to be analyzed.

4.2 Sensitivity of residues with respect to sub-models

After excluding unstable specifications (Section 4.1), a total of 764 model combinations remain. To investigate the sensitivity of fitting residues $R_{\mathcal{T},p}$ (Eqn. (5)) to the choice of sub-models, i.e. their component specifications, we visualize all fitted time courses of expected deaths D_t for 2000–2019 in Fig. 5.

The top panel of Fig. 5 overlays all 764 remaining trajectories, thereby illustrating the overall range of variation across the models’ factorial design. While this figure illustrates the variation in expected death counts across models, it does not directly assess the systematic variation of the residues with exchanging model components. Hence, Fig. 6 displays histograms of residual distributions, arranged congruently with the panels of Fig. 5. For each component, the histogram of residuals is accompanied by a colored error bar denoting the mean residual plus/minus one standard deviation, thus providing a compact measure of both systematic bias by component and dispersion across component specifications.

The following observations can be drawn: First, for the components *sex*, *age cohorts*, and *temporal resolution*, the residual distributions are broadly similar across categories. This indicates that exchanging these components does not systematically and substantially affect fitting performance of a model per se. Second, by contrast, the *forerun* length shows a clear systematic effect: longer foreruns (20 years) are associated with larger residuals, reflecting a loss of fit quality to the longer-term mortality observations when a model is calibrated, i.e. fitted, during an increasing number of years. This might be attributed to the definition of the residues, not depending linearly on the length of the forerun. Third, the choice of *demographic dataset* (DPP versus YPT) leads to measurable but comparatively small differences in the residual distributions; given the sub-

Figure 5: Expected death trajectories across model component specifications. Top panel: overlay of all 764 admissible model trajectories of expected deaths D_t during the fitting period 2000–2019 (gray lines). Lower six panels: the same trajectories, colored to distinguish the different choices within the six model components (sex treatment, demography, age cohorts, temporal resolution, forerun, mortality model form).

stantial discrepancies between the two population series in some age cohorts, this limited impact on overall fit quality is somewhat surprising. Finally, the ‘constant’ model yields residuals that are distinctly larger than those of the other models, underlining its inability to capture temporal mortality dynamics in a realistic fashion.

Overall, these results demonstrate that not all modeling choices impact the fit quality equally: whereas several components are relatively neutral, the length of the forerun, the quality of the demography data, and the choice of mortality model form are decisive for achieving an adequate and reliable fit.

To additionally capture the effect of simultaneous model component exchanges, Fig. 7 displays the average yearly residues, organized by pairs of components. Since there are six of them in total, this yields $\binom{6}{2} = 15$ panels, each corresponding to one pair of component choices. Within each panel, the mean post-hoc deviations are shown, obtained by averaging across all models that contain the given pair of components.

The ‘constant’ model form, irrespective of its partner in the pair, consistently produces exceptionally large residues, underlining its inadequacy for capturing recent mortality dynamics. A similar effect is observed for the 20-years forerun, which performs poorly across most pairings. The only setting in which the ‘constant’ model attains comparatively small residues is when combined with the ‘all-ages’ resolution. However, this very resolution interacts unfavorably with the 20-years

Figure 6: Residual distribution by model component. Histograms of post-hoc yearly deviations $R_{\mathcal{T},p}$ (Eqn. (5), variance between observation and expectation) during 2000–2019, stratified by each of the six model components (as in Fig. 5). Colored error bars above each histogram denote the mean \pm one standard deviation of the residuals. Exchanges of three of the model components (sex, age resolution, and temporal resolution) show little systematic effect on fit quality, whereas demography, model form, and forerun length in particular exert substantial impact: longer foreruns yield larger deviations, a significant fraction of models fed by DDP demography comes with particularly low deviations, and the ‘constant’ model produces the largest ones.

forerun, again resulting in inflated deviations. Conversely, particularly low residues are obtained for combinations of a 5-years forerun with the PEMM or FLEMM, as well as for the pair of a 5-years forerun and the ‘all-ages’ age resolution.

Taken together, these results emphasize that while certain components alone may not strongly affect the fitting performance, their interactions in combination can substantially amplify or mitigate model adequacy.

Figure 7: Pairwise sensitivity of residuals. Heat map of mean post-hoc yearly deviations $R_{\mathcal{T},p}$ (Eqn. (5)) during 2000–2019, averaged over all models containing a given pair of sub-model components. Each of the $\binom{6}{2} = 15$ panels corresponds to one such pair. Colors range from yellow (lowest mean deviation) to black (highest), with white cells indicating infeasible model combinations (e.g. 1-years age resolution combined with all but yearly temporal resolution). Particularly low deviations arise for 5-years foreruns paired with PEMM or FLEMM, while ‘constant’ models and 20-years foreruns generally yield the highest deviations.

4.3 Sensitivity of FVU with respect to sub-models

In addition to residuals from previous Subsection 4.2, we also investigated the FVU (Eqn. (6)) as a measure of model adequacy. Recall that $FVU < 1$ corresponds to a model that reduces the variance of the data around the mean, and therefore outperforms the latter as the simplest model possible, while $FVU > 1$ accordingly indicates that the model is inadequate.

Figure 8 summarizes the distribution of FVU values across all sub-model groups. Similar to the residual analysis, the FVU is largely unaffected by the choice of sex stratification or temporal resolution. Additionally, the choices of the demographic dataset and age-cohort resolution seem not to affect FVU at all. The most problematic specification is the ‘constant’ model, which exhibits FVU values up to 2.5, i.e. a variance that is 2.5 times the variance of the data themselves. In contrast, the GEMM shows consistently small and narrowly distributed FVU values, a consequence of the fact that unstable combinations with a 5-years forerun had already been excluded. Indeed, short foreruns in general are associated with larger FVU values, further highlighting their inadequacy.

Figure 8: Distribution of fraction of variance unexplained (FVU) across sub-models. Gray bars: histogram of FVU values for all models in the respective sub-model group. Colored markers: mean \pm standard deviation for each category. Sex, demographic dataset, and temporal resolution show little effect on FVU. The ‘all-ages’ cohort yields slightly lower values, but at the cost of inflated EM. ‘Constant’ models exhibit extremely high FVU (up to 2.5), whereas GEMM remain narrowly distributed due to exclusion of unstable 5-years forerun scenarios.

Figure 9 provides the pairwise comparison of mean FVU values across all sub-model combinations. Here, the ‘constant’ model again stands out with uniformly high FVU regardless of its partner, while the GEMM remains close to the feasible regime. The PEMM perform very similar to FLEMM, with their FVU increasing particularly when combined with short forerun. Note that

the relatively narrow range of FVU values for the GEMM stems from the exclusion of a concurrent 5-years forerun.

Taken together, these findings reinforce earlier results: ‘constant’ models should be discarded, while open and actuarial models perform more stably. FVU thus provides an additional lens confirming that model instability is driven primarily by inadequate forerun and by structural limitations of the ‘constant’ model.

Figure 9: Pairwise comparison of mean FVU across sub-model combinations. Heat map representation of mean FVU values (yellow = low, black = high; white = infeasible combinations). ‘Constant’ models consistently produce high FVU regardless of pairing, while GEMMs remain close to the feasible regime. Exponential models show increased FVU when combined with short forerun periods.

4.4 Interim evaluation of recommendations

Having examined the sensitivity of estimates using residues and FVU across the full factorial set of model components, we summarize some recommendations for future applications, before finalizing recommendations in Section 6.7.

Sex stratification. It is surprisingly immaterial whether males and females are modeled separately or pooled. Across all analyses, including pairwise interactions (cf. Figs. 5–9), no systematic differences emerged. This runs counter to actuarial practice but reflects the robustness of mortality estimates for a nearly constant population with respect to sex stratification.

Demography. Differences between the DPP and YPT population data are visible, especially in census years, yet their impact is comparatively small. We regard both as usable for reliable estimates of expected whole-population mortality, although future applications may benefit from adopting the most recent demographic series.

Age cohort resolution. Choosing a granularity of age cohort resolution below 10 years is unnecessary in terms of residuals and FVU.

Temporal resolution. Again somewhat unexpectedly, the choice of temporal resolution (yearly, monthly, weekly, or weekly with filter) exerts almost no effect on residuals and FVU.

Forerun length. In general, although the short forerun captures most recent trends, taking only 5-years seem to be numerically unstable. Whereas, on average, residua for 5-years forerun are slightly smaller than 20 year forerun, FVU values of the 5-years forerun being consistently above 0.5 rule it out in general. Long forerun (20 years) yields, on average, slightly larger (normalized) residua than only 10 years, yet consistently the smallest FVU, i.e. the highest model adequacy.

Model choice. Contrary to all other models, with both their residua and FVU values being reasonable, the ‘constant’ model is to be avoided entirely, because its FVU values are consistently the highest, and mostly even higher than 1.

5 Evaluation of model extrapolations – Sensitivity of excess mortality with respect to sub-models

The central quantity of interest is the excess mortality (EM), defined here as the yearly difference between observed and expected deaths (all model trajectories plotted in Fig. 10), see Eqn. (7), evaluated over the extrapolation period $T_{extrap.} = \{2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024\}$. By construction, EM may take negative values (under-mortality) whenever expected deaths exceed observed deaths.

Figure 10: Expected death trajectories across model specifications. Top panel: overlay of all 764 admissible model trajectories of expected deaths D_t during the extrapolation period 2020–2024 (gray lines). Lower six panels: the same trajectories, colored to distinguish the different choices within the six model components (sex treatment, demography, age cohorts, temporal resolution, forerun, mortality model form).

Single sub-model effects. Figure 11 shows histograms of EM values for each component, accompanied by colored error bars indicating the mean plus/minus one standard deviation. The following patterns emerge:

- Sex treatment and temporal resolution have virtually no impact on EM; their distributions overlap almost completely.
- With regard to demography, the choice DPP tends to increase EM slightly relative to choosing YPT.
- The aggregated ‘all-ages’ resolution yields extremely high EM values, which indicates that ignoring age heterogeneity severely distorts estimates.

- With regard to forerun length, choosing 5 years yields the lowest EM (but with high variability), whereas 10 years yields the highest EM and 20 years occupies an intermediate position.
- The ‘constant’ model produces negative EM on average, reflecting systematic overestimation of expected deaths.
- Among the model forms, the PEMM and the ‘linear’ model tend to give the highest EM. The ‘constant’ and the ‘quadratic’ models show the largest standard deviations.

Pairwise interactions. Figure 12 displays mean EM values across all $\binom{6}{2} = 15$ pairs of components in the form of heat maps (blue = negative EM, red = positive EM, white = infeasible combinations). Several systematic effects are evident:

- The ‘all-ages’ resolution dominates across all pairings: whenever chosen, EM is maximized regardless of the other component it is paired with (the second sub-model).
- The PEMM consistently yields higher EM values than other model forms, regardless of the second sub-model.
- The only settings that produce negative EM are ‘constant’ models combined with age cohort resolutions finer than ‘all-ages’ (i.e. 10-year, 5-year, or 1-year cohorts). Conversely, the ‘constant’ model combined with ‘all-ages’ produces absurdly high EM values (roughly 75.000 per year). An effect not seen for the ‘linear’ or ‘quadratic’ model.
- The PEMM interacts sensitively with forerun lengths, with both short (5-year) and long (20-year) foreruns yielding higher EM values. The ‘quadratic’ and ‘linear’ model yield exceptionally large EM (up to 70.000 per year) when combined with 10 or 20 years forerun, respectively.
- Comparatively low EM values are achieved by combinations involving the FLEMM or GEMM with 1-years cohorts, as well as the pairing of a 20-years forerun with 1-years cohorts.

In summary, while several components (sex, temporal resolution) appear largely irrelevant for EM, both *age cohort resolution* and *model form* play a decisive role, and their *interactions with forerun length* can substantially amplify or attenuate EM estimates.

Figure 11: EM by sub-model component. Histogram plots of EM values during 2020–2024 for each of the six components (sex, demography, age cohorts, temporal resolution, forerun, mortality model form). Colored error bars indicate mean EM \pm one standard deviation. Sex treatment and temporal resolution have negligible impact, while old demographic data lead to slightly higher EM. The ‘all-ages’ resolution produces extremely high EM, the ‘constant’ model yields negative EM on average, and forerun length (especially 10 years) and model form (PEMM) strongly impact EM magnitude.

Figure 12: Pairwise interactions of EM. Heat maps of mean EM values during 2020–2024, averaged across all models that include each specific pair of sub-model components ($\binom{6}{2} = 15$ panels). Colors encode EM values, with blue indicating negative EM, red indicating positive EM, and color intensity reflecting magnitude; white cells mark infeasible model combinations (e.g. 1-years cohorts with weekly resolution). Across all pairings, the ‘all-ages’ resolution produces the highest EM, the PEMM consistently yields higher EM than alternatives, and the ‘constant’ model produces negative EM when combined with finer age stratifications but extremely high EM when combined with ‘all-ages’. Relatively low EM is found for FLEMM or PEMM combined with 1-years cohorts, or for 20-years foreruns with 1-years cohorts.

6 Discussion

6.1 Age cohort resolution and Simpson’s paradox

A striking and consistent pattern across all model forms is the emergence of Simpson’s paradox [22, fig. 2]: if age heterogeneity is ignored by collapsing the population into a single ‘all-ages’ cohort, then EM estimates become systematically inflated. The paradox itself lies in the fact that, for all age cohorts, mortality rates have been decreasing tendentially for the last 25 years, while the mortality rate for the whole population has been simultaneously increasing. For example, in the linear model the ‘all-ages’ cohort has an *increasing* trend term $\lambda_{\text{all}} = 0.008$ whereas for the 10-years age groups all trends are in the range $[-0.021, -0.007]$ except the age range 90+ with $\lambda_{90+} = 0.002$. This effect is visible across all exponential-type mortality models (purely exponential, PEMM, finite-limit exponential, FLEMM, and generalized exponential, GEMM), but it is most dramatic in the ‘constant’ model (see Section 6.3).

Figure 13 illustrates the phenomenon in aggregate by highlighting in red all models without demographic resolution (‘all-ages’ cohort). It is clearly seen that these models consistently occupy the lower edge of the expected-deaths corridor, thereby yielding the highest EM values across specifications, see also Fig. 12. By contrast, models with age stratification occupy the upper corridor and remain more stable, even across different mortality model forms.

Figure 13: Impact of the ‘all-ages’ cohort resolution. Gray lines: Expected death trajectories of all feasible models during 2000–2024. Red lines: models without demographic resolution (‘all-ages’ cohort), which consistently lie on the lower edge of the expected-deaths corridor and yield inflated EM estimates. By contrast, models with age stratification remain concentrated in the upper corridor. This pattern, observed across all mortality model forms, reflects Simpson’s paradox in aggregated mortality data and motivates discarding ‘all-ages’-cohort and ‘constant’ models from EM analyses.

These results strongly suggest that models lacking age-cohort resolution should be excluded from serious excess-mortality analyses. Such models introduce systematic bias through aggregation effects, obscure the role of demographic change in shaping population-level mortality, and yield result corridors that are not only excessively wide but also demographically implausible. In particular, neglecting age stratification ignores the well-known Simpson paradox: population-level mortality trends can change purely due to shifts in the age structure, even if age-specific mortality remains stable or declines. By collapsing all ages into a single category, information about this fundamental driver of all-cause mortality is discarded. It is therefore unsurprising that models

fitted solely at the aggregate ‘all-ages’ level tend to produce biased and, in many cases, unreliable extrapolations of expected mortality. Among the extrapolative approaches considered, linear models appear least susceptible to this effect, though they do not eliminate it. Moreover, models without age cohort resolution preclude meaningful comparison across populations, as standard age-standardized mortality measures cannot be computed. For these reasons, age-stratified modeling should be regarded as a minimal methodological requirement in future excess-mortality studies.

6.2 Reasonable forerun length

The length of the forerun, i.e. the number of historical years included for fitting, has a pronounced effect, see Figs. 16, 17, and 18.

In general, the 5-years forerun produces large FVU values, see Figure 8, likely reflecting over-parameterization relative to data availability, and therefore should be avoided. On the other hand, the 20-years forerun produces slightly increased residuals, which may also be a consequence of the normalization coefficient in Eqn. (5). As an interim result, we suggest to favor 10-years forerun slightly over 20-years forerun, if short- or medium-term extrapolations like in our setting for the years 2020–2024 are to be investigated.

6.3 The ‘constant’ model

Figure 14 provides a notable perspective, when focusing on the ‘constant’ model only. All feasible EM trajectories are shown in gray, with ‘constant’ models highlighted, and acknowledging any age cohort resolution emphasized in green. The latter tend to predict under-mortality during 2020–2024 and thus form the upper bound of the EM corridor, whereas ‘constant’ and ‘all-ages’-cohort models anchor the lower bound with implausibly high EM. The spread between these extremes widens further for long foreruns (10 or 20 years), producing corridors of EM estimates that are demographically implausible.

Figure 14: Effects of ‘constant’ model versus age cohort resolution. Gray lines: Death-time courses of all feasible models during 2000–2024. Green lines: models with any age cohort resolution (10-year, 5-year, or 1-year), which systematically predict under-mortality and form the upper bound of the EM corridor. ‘Constant’ models (highlighted) illustrate their erratic performance, producing negative EM with finer resolutions but extremely high EM with the ‘all-ages’ cohort. The corridor between these extremes expands further with longer foreruns, leading to implausible ranges of EM.

Taken together, ‘constant’ models, should be *discarded* in serious EM analyses. They produce

inflated FVU values and residuals, and introduce systematic bias due to aggregation effects and produce corridors of results that are not only wide but also demographically implausible.

6.4 ‘Linear’ and ‘quadratic’ models

In addition to the ‘constant’ specification, we also investigated ‘linear’ and ‘quadratic’ extrapolation models. Both reproduce mortality probabilities well during the respective forerun periods up to 2019, but exhibit substantial deficiencies when extrapolated into the years 2020–2024. Figure 15 illustrates the impact of age-cohort resolution on the performance of these two models.

For the ‘linear’ model, incorporating age-cohort resolution (red lines) yields extrapolations that are generally plausible and remain within a moderately bounded corridor, although noticeable dispersion across cohort specifications persists. By contrast, omitting age-cohort resolution entirely (the ‘all-ages’ resolution; yellow lines) leads to a markedly increased spread of extrapolated mortality trajectories. In this aggregated setting, the linear extrapolation becomes unstable, indicating that collapsing heterogeneous age-specific trends into a single time series substantially degrades robustness.

The ‘quadratic’ model performs even more problematically. Already under the ‘all-ages’ specification (green lines), extrapolations display a wide dispersion, reflecting the intrinsic sensitivity of quadratic fits to small changes in the calibration window. When age-cohort resolution is introduced (blue lines), this instability is further amplified: extrapolated mortality trajectories diverge dramatically, yielding both severe over- and underestimations in 2020–2024. This unreliable performance suggests that the additional degrees of freedom inherent to quadratic models interact unfavorably with demographic stratification, rendering the resulting extrapolations highly unreliable. In addition it seems that the quadratic model diverges to $\pm\infty$ rapidly after the end of the fitting period underscoring that polynomial extrapolations are ill-suited for constructing meaningful counterfactual mortality baselines in this context, see [22, app. C] for a particular example.

Figure 15: Impact of age cohort resolution in ‘linear’ and ‘quadratic’ models. Grey lines: expected death-time curves from all feasible models (2000–2024). ‘Linear’ model: ‘all-ages’ cohort in red, age-stratified cohorts in yellow. ‘Quadratic’ model: ‘all-ages’ cohort in green, age-stratified cohorts in blue. While the ‘linear’ model remains within a narrow corridor regardless of cohort resolution, the ‘quadratic’ model becomes highly unstable when applied to stratified cohorts.

Figure 16 displays the sensitivity of both model forms to the length of the forerun. For the ‘linear’ model, the 5-years (red lines) and 20-years (blue lines) foreruns systematically deviate from the 10-years forerun (green lines). For the 5-years forerun (already excluded above) the

information of the 2019 mortality dip may be overly passed on to extrapolation very likely leading to a systematic underestimation of expected deaths. By contrast, the 10-years forerun represents an intermediate, yielding plausibly moderate extrapolations of expected mortality. The long 20-years forerun maybe underestimates recent mortality trends 2010–2019, and thus is on the lower edge of the mortality prediction 2020–2024.

The ‘quadratic’ model displays even greater sensitivity. A 20-years forerun produces vast overestimation of mortality, likely reflecting the upward curvature of the parabola’s ascending branch. With 10 years of forerun, the ‘quadratic’ fit instead tends to systematically underestimate mortality, though the mechanism remains unclear to the authors. The 5-years forerun produces the most erratic outputs: predictions for 2022–2024 become widely spread, with some realizations falling below 900,000 expected deaths in 2024, which is demographically implausible. This suggests that the ‘quadratic’ model from has too many (i.e. three) degrees of freedom compared to the five years it is supposed to capture mortality trends, making it unsuitable for reliable EM estimation as already mentioned above.

Taken together, the ‘linear’ model may serve as a simple extrapolation tool, provided that a forerun of preferably 10 years is used. The ‘quadratic’ model, by contrast, is prone to severe instability and raises divergence issues, particularly when combined with demographic resolution or short foreruns, and should therefore be avoided in practice.

6.5 The actuarial models

The most commonly used models are the actuarial models including exponential terms.

For the PEMM, the length of the forerun, i.e. the number of historical years included for fitting, has a pronounced effect. Figure 17 displays all expected death-time curves in gray, highlighting PEMM according to forerun length: 5-years (red), 10-years (green), and 20-years (blue). The 5-years and 20-years foreruns systematically deviate from the 10-years forerun. The 10-years forerun occupies the middle of the death-time corridor, whereas both 5-years and 20-years foreruns tend to the lower bound, producing higher EM estimates. It seems that the forerun has essential impact on different trends that are reflected, maybe due to a possible change of the mortality trend during the long-term (20-year) forerun, see e.g. [30] for a similar problem for UK. A good forerun choice depends on the concrete problem and the question which should be answered. As a preferable ‘mean’ choice we recommend the 10-years forerun.

This sensitivity on the forerun length, which leads to results concentrated on different EM estimates, seems to depend on the model form. Figure 18 shows the corresponding results for the FLEMM, with the same color coding. Here, no systematic displacement between different forerun lengths is observed. The FLEMM therefore appears more stable with respect to the choice of forerun, and for a given forerun more sensitive with respect to other model parameters, with the exception of age cohort resolution – see ‘all-age’ versus other cohort resolutions in Fig. 12.

The GEMM with 5-years forerun or with weekly resolution was already disqualified due to unstable performance, likely reflecting over-parameterization relative to data availability. With a 10-years or 20-years forerun and monthly or yearly resolution, this model seems to yield reasonable results.

Summarizing, we recommend the PEMM and the GEMM in combination with a 10-years forerun, and the FLEMM with a 10-years or 20-years forerun. In actuarial contexts, most likely the PEMM is used due to its simple adjustment properties. From a general point of view, the property that all mortality probabilities tend to zero is a serious disadvantage, and we therefore recommend the use of FLEMM or GEMM also for actuarial purposes.

6.6 Impact of demographic data

A further dimension in our factorial design concerns the choice of demographic data: the DPP versus the YPT series, both provided by Destatis. Despite the fact that certain age cohorts differ in size by up to 80% between these datasets (see Fig. 2), the impact on residuals and FVU turned out

Figure 16: Impact of forerun length in ‘linear’ and ‘quadratic’ models. Top panel: ‘linear’ model with 5-years (red), 10-years (green), and 20-years (blue) forerun. Short and long forerun underestimate mortality, while the 10-years forerun provides the most stable extrapolation. Bottom panel: ‘quadratic’ model with identical color coding. Here, 20-years forerun vastly overestimates, 10-years forerun underestimates, and 5-years forerun produces implausibly wide spreads (even $< 900,000$ deaths in 2024). ‘Quadratic’ models thus appear structurally unsuitable for robust EM estimation.

surprisingly moderate, see Figs. 6–9. For EM estimation, however, there are systematic differences observable, see Figs. 11 and 12.

Figure 19 compares expected death-time curves from 2000–2024 using DPP (red) versus YPT (green) demographic data. The time courses display distinct features linked to the choice of demography. In the period 2004–2008 YPT produces markedly higher expected deaths than observed, whereas the DPP fits this interval more closely. Moreover, for the YPT dataset, sharp peaks occur at the census year 2011, whereas the DPP dataset shows corresponding peaks around 2010. One possible explanation is that different back-projection of population counts based on the 2011 census may have introduced distortions into the earlier years. The extrapolation for the years 2020–2024 predicts consistently higher mortality using the YPT data than for the DPP data, and thus EM is markedly higher for the DDP than for the YPT.

Figure 17: Impact of forerun length in the PEMM. Gray lines: expected death-time curves from all feasible models (2000–2024). Highlighted: PEMM with 5-years forerun (red), 10-years (green), and 20-years (blue). While 10-years forerun lies in the middle of the death-time corridor, both 5-years and 20-years fall to the lower bound, yielding higher EM. Statistical testing confirms significant differences in mean EM ($p \ll 0.001$) between 5-years vs. 10-years and 20-years vs. 10-year.

Figure 18: Impact of forerun length in the FLEMM. Gray lines: expected death-time curves from all feasible models (2000–2024). Highlighted: FLEMM with 5-years (red), 10-years (green), and 20-years (blue) foreruns. In contrast to the purely exponential mortality model, no systematic displacement or significant differences between forerun lengths are observed. The refined model therefore provides more stable EM estimates across forerun periods.

Perceived historical anomalies like EM peaks in census years, or EM estimates back-projected from such, should be re-considered with particular care. Since both datasets are provided by the German Federal Statistical Office and use the same underlying population counts, it is unclear to the authors where the difference comes from and which data set should be considered as more ‘realistic’ and used for EM estimates.

Figure 19: Effect of demographic data choice. Red lines: DPP, demographic data from the population pyramid; green lines: YPT, demographic data from population tables. Overall differences in EM are small, with new data yielding slightly lower EM estimates on average ($p \approx 0.022$). Distinct peaks occur at the census years (2010–2011), and deviations are notable in 2004–2008, where the new data overestimate mortality relative to observations.

6.7 Synthesis of recommendations

Having examined the sensitivity of residuals, FVU, and EM estimates across the full factorial set of model components, we finalize our recommendations (Section 4.4) for estimating mortality in Germany (or any constant population) during a forerun period, in which observed data are fitted, and extrapolating these fitted estimations to another five years.

Sex stratification. As for the residua and FVU, it is surprisingly immaterial for estimating whole-population mortality whether males and females are modeled separately or pooled. Across all analyses, including pairwise interactions (cf. Fig. 12), no systematic differences emerged. This runs counter to actuarial intuition but reflects the robustness of EM estimates for the relatively constant German population with respect to sex stratification. Modelers may be free to choose from both options.

Demography. As shown in Section 6.6, substantial differences between DPP and YPT population data are visible, especially in census years, yet their impact on residuals and FVU is comparatively moderate. For EM, however, we observed systematic differences. We regard both data sets as usable, although future applications may benefit from adopting the most recent demographic series.

Age cohort resolution. Contrary to sex stratification, the choice of age cohort resolution is decisive for EM estimation. Models without age stratification (‘all-ages’ cohort) systematically produce inflated EM values due to Simpson’s paradox, as discussed in Section 6.1. We therefore conclude that models without demographic resolution should be avoided. All other age cohort resolutions yield more moderate EM results.

Temporal resolution. Somewhat unexpectedly, the choice of temporal resolution (yearly, monthly, weekly, or weekly with filter) exerts almost no effect on yearly EM estimates or on residuals. This

implies that finer temporal grids may be chosen for purposes of visualization or short-term analysis, but they do not impact long-term EM calculations. This finding is reassuring for contexts or countries where only coarse temporal mortality data in the forerun period are available. As a point of consideration, choosing high-parametric models (e.g. GEMM) together with finer resolution may yield to over-parametrization and divergent extrapolations (Fig. 4).

Forerun length. In general, models with 5-years forerun are numerically unstable, tend to overestimate EM and should be avoided, as discussed in Section 3.5, 20-years forerun produces slightly increased residuals and may miss more recent trends. Hence we recommend (at least) 10-years forerun lengths for the extrapolation years 2020-2024.

Model choice. ‘Constant’ and ‘quadratic’ models should be avoided entirely, as they produce implausible and contradictory EM estimates, particularly when extrapolating. The ‘linear’ model may serve as a simple extrapolation, provided that a moderately long (i.e. 10-year) forerun is used.

All actuarial models (PEMM, FLEMM, GEMM) seem suitable frameworks for EM estimation, when used with at least 10-years forerun length. The GEMM is flexible and may be the most natural model, yet proved unstable in our setting with fine (i.e. weekly) temporal resolution, due to the higher number of parameters. Hence we recommend all three models with at least 10-years forerun.

Summary. Figure 20 visualizes the set of models retained under these considerations against the background of all herein analyzed models, which are displayed as gray lines in Fig. 20. As a minimum set of recommendations, we excluded all ‘constant’ and ‘quadratic’ models, 5 year forerun periods, the ‘all-age’ cohort resolution, as well as GEMM with 10-years forerun and weekly resolution (see Fig. 4). We call the remaining models the *recommended models*. To particularly show the impact of variable demographic data, we evaluated, other than in Fig. 19, only these models, once again distinguished by both conditions (YPT: green lines; DDP: red lines).

Summary. Figure 20 illustrates the subset of models retained under the methodological considerations discussed above, shown in relation to the full ensemble of models analyzed in this study. For reference, all models are displayed as gray lines in Fig. 20. As a minimal set of recommendations, we excluded all ‘constant’ and ‘quadratic’ extrapolation models, all configurations using a 5-year forerun, the ‘all-ages’ cohort resolution, as well as the GEMM combined with a 10-year forerun at weekly resolution (cf. Fig. 4). The models remaining after these exclusions are referred to as the *recommended models*. To highlight the impact of alternative demographic inputs, we re-evaluated this reduced model set – similar to Fig. 19 – using both population datasets, distinguishing results based on YPT (green lines) and DPP (red lines).

6.8 Assessment against literature

To further assess the validity of our findings, we juxtaposed the EM estimates obtained in this study with those reported by institutional and academic sources. Figure 21 summarizes the model-derived EM (all analyzed models: gray errorbars; recommended models with DPP: red errorbars; recommended models with YPT: green errorbars) alongside literature estimates (other symbols).

The official estimates published by the Destatis [25] and the World Health Organization (WHO) [14, 19] show striking discrepancies in the first pandemic year. In 2020, these sources suggest between 40,000 and 70,000 excess deaths, while our models consistently yield values in the range of 0–20,000. The initial WHO spline-based extrapolation even suggested an implausible 125,000 excess deaths in 2021 – a result that would predict negative mortality if extrapolated further, a well-known artifact of spline methods [12, 27]. By 2021, the corrected WHO estimates and Destatis values converge, but still indicate $\sim 70,000$ excess deaths, clearly above the 25,000–50,000 range supported by our model ensemble. This overestimation is likely due to the omission of demographic

Figure 20: Recommended models for EM estimation versus all analyzed models (764 total). Red and green lines show *recommended* models with DPP and YPT data (each 104 total), respectively, defined by exclusion of ‘constant’ models, 5-years forerun, models without age cohort resolution, all ‘quadratic’ models, and ‘linear’ models or PEMM with 20-years forerun. This reduced set represents the most robust basis for future EM estimation.

resolution (aggregated ‘all-ages’ cohort) in the institutional models. From 2022 onward, Destatis estimates (60,000–80,000 in 2022, 20,000–40,000 in 2023, and approximately no excess in 2024) align more closely with the range of our models.

Several PEMMs for Germany have been published [5, 7, 17]. Their estimates fall within the range of our *recommended* models – particularly with the ones using YPT – supporting the robustness of actuarial approaches when applied with appropriate demographic stratification and moderate forerun lengths. A FLEMM by Rockenfeller et al. [22] consistently yielded approximately 20,000 fewer excess deaths than comparable PEMMs. During further investigation [21], the same model found this difference owing to a combination of using YPT instead of DPP, 5-years instead of 10-years age cohorts, and weekly instead of yearly temporal resolution, whose exchange reduced EM differences to mere 5,000-10,000. Baum [2] reported unusually low EM estimates for a ‘quadratic’ model. As discussed in Section 6.4, ‘quadratic’ extrapolations typically produce volatile outputs; the apparent stability of Baum’s estimates most likely arises from the use of *interpolation* across 2000–2021 rather than using extrapolation, thus differing methodologically from our approach. Finally, Kowall et al. [16] compared a ‘constant’ versus an exponential baseline for 2020, obtaining EM estimates of $-22,000$ and $+10,000$, respectively, illustrating the sensitivity of EM to baseline model choice, even within a single year. A similar comparison between a ‘constant’ (median) and a (not further specified) “binomial regression” model [29] yielded within-years differences between 30,000 and 40,000 excess deaths for 2020-2022. Note that the corresponding values displayed in Fig. 21 were manually extracted from [29, fig. 2].

Taken together, these literature comparisons strengthen our recommendations (Sections 4.4, 6.7): ‘constant’ and ‘quadratic’ models should be avoided; updated demographic data should be preferred; age cohort resolution, combined with exponential-type models (preferably PEMM and FLEMM), over a medium (10-years) to long (20-years) forerun period represents the most meaningful and robust approach to estimating EM.

year	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
observed deaths	985,572	1,023,687	1,066,341	1,028,206	1,005,550
modeled deaths and EM					
all analyzed models	967,179	971,988	972,249	980,271	990,898
	$18,392 \pm 17,900$	$51,699 \pm 23,516$	$94,092 \pm 30,136$	$47,935 \pm 33,819$	$14,652 \pm 40,144$
recommended models (DPP)	976,496	980,080	972,030	984,743	1,001,557
	$9,076 \pm 9,082$	$43,607 \pm 10,451$	$94,311 \pm 11,129$	$43,463 \pm 12,050$	$3,993 \pm 13,683$
recommended models (YPT)	986,570	999,076	1,008,269	1,011,857	1,022,520
	$-998 \pm 4,291$	$24,611 \pm 6,361$	$58,072 \pm 7,170$	$16,349 \pm 6,778$	$-16,970 \pm 6,824$

Figure 21: Comparison of model-derived EM estimates with literature. Top table lists observed deaths, modeled deaths, and the resulting mean EM estimates (plus-minus standard deviation) for 2020–2024 of all analyzed models as well as of recommended and strongly recommended models. Bottom graphic displays this EM for analyzed models (red error bars), recommended models (gray error bars), and strongly recommended models (green error bars) alongside institutional and academic literature estimates. Institutional models (Destatis [25], WHO [14, 19]) tend to overestimate EM, particularly in 2020–2021, likely due to inadequate demographic resolution and spline-based extrapolations. Academic actuarial models [5, 7, 16, 17, 21] fall within the strongly recommended range, while ‘quadratic’ [2] and ‘constant’ models [16] yield implausible or contradictory results.

Statements and Declarations

Competing Interests: The author declares that no financial support was received from any organization for the submitted work. The author declares that he has no financial relationships at present or within the previous three years with any organizations that might have an interest in the submitted work.

Use of AI tools: A large language model (LLM) was used to assist with linguistic refinements of the manuscript. The LLM did not contribute to the research design, data analysis, model development, interpretation of results, or conceptual content of this study. All scientific decisions, analyses, and conclusions remain solely the responsibility of the authors.

Supplementary Material

- Table (`Deaths_diff.D.xlsx`) with death counts in Germany wrt age cohorts in 2019 before and after the plausibility check
- Table (`Deaths_diff.BL.xlsx`) with death counts in Germany wrt states in 2019 before and after the plausibility check
- Table (`Data_all.csv`) with estimated deaths per year 2000-2024 wrt each of the model evaluations.

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